

Differential Flatness of Electric Power Systems

by

Lucas E Uecker

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment
of the Requirements for the Degree of
Master of Science in Electrical Engineering

New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology
Socorro, New Mexico
December, 2014

ABSTRACT

This thesis shows that the flux-decay model of a synchronous generator exhibits the property of differential flatness. This property is used for trajectory planning of simple power systems, where generators are represented by flux-decay models, as the property allows for one-to-one correspondence between the inputs of a system and particular (flat) outputs. The flat outputs of the generators are taken to be the injected network-frame currents, with control inputs being the exciter reference voltages and the turbine speed governor set-points. The utility of differential flatness is shown for open loop control of a single machine, infinite-bus system, a simple linearizing feedback controller for a multi-machine system as well as a simple tracking application in a multi-machine system with time varying loads. These sample applications show that flatness-based methods can enable coordinated control for both the multiple inputs of a generator, but also may be used as part of feedback control of a generator or power system involving multiple generators. Sensitivity of the flatness approach to uncertainty in the model and its parameters is explored. Model uncertainty is investigated by implementation of flatness-based control on a higher order model, and parameter uncertainty is investigated via application of trajectory sensitivities. These tests show the extent to which parameters needed for trajectory planning affect transient and steady-state tracking errors.

Keywords: Differential Flatness; Nonlinear Control; Power Generation; Trajectory Planning; Modeling; Simulation;

CONTENTS

LIST OF TABLES	iv
LIST OF FIGURES	v
1. INTRODUCTION	1
2. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION	4
2.1 The Power System	4
2.1.1 The One-Axis Generator Model	5
2.1.2 Power Network: Transmission Lines and Loads	8
2.2 Differential Flatness	10
2.2.1 Example of Differential Flatness	11
3. FLATNESS OF THE GENERATOR MODEL	13
4. OPEN-LOOP CONTROL OF THE SMIB SYSTEM	17
4.1 Trajectory Generation	17
4.2 Simulation Results	18
5. LINEARIZING FEEDBACK OF A 9-BUS SYSTEM	22
5.1 The 9-Bus System with Constant Impedance-Type Loads	22
5.1.1 Line Impedances	22
5.1.2 Constant Impedance Loads	22
5.2 Flatness-based Linearizing Feedback	24
5.2.1 Control Objective	27
5.3 Simulation Results	28
6. CONTROL OF 9-BUS SYSTEM WITH TIME-VARYING DEMAND	31
6.1 Constant Control Results	32
6.2 Feedback Controlled Results	32

7. EFFECTS OF ERROR IN MODEL AND PARAMETERS	42
7.1 Model Error	42
7.2 Parameter Error	43
8. CONCLUSION	49
A. DERIVATION OF WARD EQUIVALENTS	51
A.1 Two-Section Ward Equivalent	51
A.2 Three-Section Ward Equivalent	52
A.3 Ward Feedback Method	54
B. POLYNOMIAL TRAJECTORY PLANNING	56
B.1 Polynomial Fitting Between Two Steady States	56
B.2 Polynomial Perturbation Function	57
REFERENCES	58

LIST OF TABLES

5.1	9-Bus Admittance Matrix Line Components	23
5.2	9-Bus Admittance Matrix Line-Charging Components	23
5.3	9-Bus Admittance Matrix Load Components	23
5.4	9-Bus Initial System Data	28
6.1	Load Current Steady State Values	31

LIST OF FIGURES

2.1	Synchronous Generator Diagram	6
2.2	Pi Model of a Transmission Line	9
2.3	A Block Diagram of Power System Components	10
2.4	Buck-Type DC-to-DC Converter	11
4.1	Single Machine Infinite Bus	19
4.2	Open-Loop Control Scheme	19
4.3	Desired and Resulting Real and Imaginary Injected Current	19
4.4	P_C Generated for Open-Loop SMIB Control	20
4.5	V_{ref} Generated for Open-Loop SMIB Control	21
5.1	One-line Diagram of the 9-Bus System	24
5.2	Closed-Loop Control Scheme for The Linearizing Feedback	26
5.3	Real Generator Currents due to 9-Bus Linearizing Feedback	29
5.4	Imaginary Generator Currents due to 9-Bus Linearizing Feedback	30
6.1	Time-Varying Load Model	32
6.2	Feedback Control Scheme	34
6.3	9-Bus Terminal Voltage Magnitude: Constant Control	34
6.4	9-Bus Terminal Voltage Angle: Constant Control	35
6.5	9-Bus Terminal Real Current: Constant Control	36
6.6	9-Bus Terminal Reactive Current: Constant Control	37
6.7	9-Bus Terminal Voltage Magnitude: Feedback Control	38
6.8	9-Bus Terminal Voltage Angle: Feedback Control	39
6.9	9-Bus Terminal Real Current: Feedback Control	40
6.10	9-Bus Terminal Imaginary Current: Feedback Control	41
7.1	Error in Flat Outputs due to SMIB Modeling Error	44
7.2	SMIB Trajectory Sensitivities: Real Current (1)	45
7.3	SMIB Trajectory Sensitivities: Real Current (2)	46

7.4	SMIB Trajectory Sensitivities: Imaginary Current (1)	47
7.5	SMIB Trajectory Sensitivities: Imaginary Current (2)	48
A.1	Reduction of 9-bus System to Equivalent 3-bus	52

This thesis is accepted on behalf of the faculty of the Institute by the following committee:

Kevin Wedeward

Kevin Wedeward, Advisor

Scott Teare

Steve Schaffer

I release this document to the New Mexico Institute of Mining and Technology.

Lucas Uecker

Lucas E Uecker

Date

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

Proper operation of a power system requires constant matching of the energy put into the system by power generators and energy consumed at the terminating end of the system and energy lost in transmission. Controlling generators to respond to changes in loading is challenging due to the fact that generator dynamics are both non-linear and involve effects at a wide variety of time scales, as well as the fact that generators are coupled together in a power system, outlined in Glover et al, as well as Kundur et al [1, 2].

Synchronous power generators, like most electric power generators, use an rotating magnetic field relative to conductor coils to create and electromotive force. The amount of magnetic flux density needed for industrial generation requires that the field be generated using a electromagnetic coil, called a “field coil”, rather than a permanent magnet. This requires an energy source, typically another generator device or another set of generator coils in the same generator structure. This energy must be conditioned and controlled by a voltage regulator. The voltage regulator typically compares some reference voltage to the generator output voltage magnitude and adjusts the field voltage appropriately. This reference voltage forms the first point of control of the generator dynamics. The detailed development of the generator mathematical model is developed in Sauer and Pai [3].

The second input of both control and power into a synchronous generator is the torque to the rotor. The power supplied to the rotor must ensure that the machine is as close to synchronous angular velocity as possible, which means this input power must match power extracted electrically as well as power lost mechanically.

Any acceleration by the rotor will alter the phase angle of the output electromotive force of the generator. This angle determines the average power generated versus the reactive power generated or stored. This angle also defines a transformation that relates the phase angles of the voltages and currents of the generator, reckoned in the “machine reference” and the voltages and currents used to define power flow of the transmission grid in the “network reference”.

The transmission of electric power is done with 3-phase alternating current. The arrangement of high voltage transmission lines, transformers, compensating capacitors, and terminating loads can be modeled as complex impedances, assuming that generated frequency does not vary substantially.

A variety of dynamic problems can occur to a power system, outlined in Kundur et al [2, 4]. These problems can be grouped into three types of instability: voltage, angle, and frequency. These are the broadest classifications that can also vary in scale and duration.

Voltage instability is a condition where the system is unable to maintain desirable operating voltages. Most often, this is a result of the system being unable to meet reactive power demand. Often, voltage problems can also occur due to the machine angle between machines, or groups of machines, having enough of an angular difference to cause under-voltage conditions at intermediate points in the network.

Angular instability often occurs when there is a significant change in loading, leading to a power mismatch between the output “electrical torque” of the generator and the input mechanical torque. This causes an acceleration or deceleration in the rotor, altering the machine angle. Significant movement of the machine angle will alter the phasor voltages and currents of the generator and therefore affect the efficiency in which power is transferred.

Frequency instability is the most non-generic of large scale power problems, but the effect is that of angular instabilities over time and several generators. Acceleration in one generator can cause acceleration of other generators on the network. The original generator may control itself back to proper synchronous speed, but can be accelerated again by other generators which it accelerated previously. This is generally a network-wide effect, with oscillations on the order of 1-3Hz.

Power system stability, in all forms, is defined as the ability for a network to reject disturbances and maintain desired operating conditions. For a power system to maintain these desired operating conditions, all generators must maintain proper balance of input/output torques as well as balance of reactive power. It is the purpose of a control system at the generator to determine the necessary inputs, in the form of field voltage and input mechanical torque, to meet proper dynamic conditions.

To ensure the stability of a system, as well as to plan trajectories and other desirable tasks, it is necessary to capture as much detailed physical behavior of the system as possible in a mathematical model. This mathematical model relates some input of the system (in the case of the generator, the reference voltage and governor setting) to the states of the system as these states evolve over time. The task of controlling a model depends on the type of system. Linear systems are generally the most simple to control, as explained in Sontag [5], but comprise only a portion of systems of engineering interest. Nonlinear systems require different techniques, also explained in Sontag, as well as in Vidyasagar [5, 6], to control a system either generally or by some local linearization.

A common method of nonlinear control is a feedback linearization. Feedback linearization is the process of making a general control system equivalent (have the same solutions as) a linear system via a well chosen feedback scheme. Feedback linearization of power systems has previously been performed in Mak

and Chapman et al [7, 8], but such feedback linearizations are constructed to linearize a system about a particular point in the state space. Such a point would correspond to a desirable operating point of a power system. Unfortunately, changes in operating conditions (change in loads or power transfers) would cause the desirable operating point to change, thus requiring the feedback linearization to be re-computed.

A result in nonlinear control theory, outlined in Murray et al as well as in Lévine [9, 10], has shown that feedback linearizability of a system is equivalent to the system having the property of “differential flatness”. A flat system has a nonlinear relationship between its inputs and an equal number of particular outputs. These “flat outputs” and their derivatives can determine states of the system as well as the inputs of the system. A trivial application of this property is that if a desired trajectory of these flat outputs and their derivatives are specified, the input required to produce these outputs from the system dynamics are pre-computed.

While this open-loop control approach can effectively steer state dynamics, it requires total knowledge of both parameters and any autonomous variations. A more general and useful method for differential flatness is to specify a control law that uses the desired progression of states, as in the open-loop case, but also incorporates state measurement such that the net effect of the controller steers error toward zero.

This thesis will show the differential flatness property of a generator’s dynamic model as well as its application to feedback control. The dynamic model for power generators will be discussed, as well as the coupling of generators via transmission lines.

The details of differential flatness of the generator model will be shown, with a trivial application given and verification. Next, a feedback scheme will be proposed as an application to coordinated generator control. An example of limited tracking of a power system with time-varying loads is then briefly explored. The effect of model parameter error on the method is then discussed. Chapter 2 will present the power system model in detail, as well as describe and give an example of the flatness property. Chapter 3 will show the flatness property of the model. Chapter 4 will demonstrate a trajectory planning application of flatness on a trivial power system. Chapter 5 demonstrates the use of flatness in a generator linearizing feedback scheme in a multi-machine setting with constant impedance type loads. Chapter 6 demonstrates a flatness-based feedback scheme in a multi-machine system with time-varying loads. Chapter 7 examines the effect of error in the model and parameters. Chapter 8 will conclude this thesis.

CHAPTER 2

BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

2.1 The Power System

The presentation of the power system model is composed of two sections. The first section is the generator dynamic model, and the second the transmission network's algebraic equations along with load modeling.

Electrical generation and transmission is accomplished using 3-phase alternating current. 3-phase power is advantageous in that it allows for constant power transfer through the generator using alternating current (which is simple to generate and transform), as well as having the advantage of requiring no neutral return conductor under balanced operation, as described in Glover et al [1]. For the purposes of this model, balanced loads and transmission will be assumed. With balanced operation assumed, there is no substantial difference between a, b, or c phases other than relative phase angle.

It is useful to adopt a reference frame that is synchronous to the rotation of the generator rotor, described in Sauer and Pai [3]. The reference frame employed is shown in figure 2.1. The field coil, fd , of the rotor defines magnetic north along the "d" (direct) axis. The perpendicular "q" (quadrature) axis can be defined as leading or lagging the d-axis with respect to direction of rotation, which are equivalent but affect model constants accordingly. This thesis will follow the convention in Sauer and Pai [3], which is shown in figure 2.1.

Generator voltages and currents can be described in either a network or machine angular reference frame. Both frames describe the same physical phenomena, but are rotated in the complex plane from each other by an angle defined by the difference in mechanical and electrical phase angles.

$$\delta \equiv \frac{P}{2}\theta_{shaft} - \omega_s t \quad (2.1)$$

where P is the number of poles of the generator (sets of a,b,c coils) and θ_{shaft} is the physical angular displacement between the rotor's "d" axis versus a reference point in the machine, typically the a-axis. The angle θ_{elec} is the electrical phase angle. The angular velocity of the rotor is then defined to be

$$\omega \equiv \frac{2}{P} \frac{d\theta_{shaft}}{dt}. \quad (2.2)$$

Machine referenced quantities (here current I_g and voltage V_g) are denoted

$$\begin{aligned} I_g &= I_d + jI_q \\ V_g &= V_d + jV_q \end{aligned}$$

where d subscripts denote real, and q subscripts denote imaginary components in the rotating machine frame. The g subscripts denote a combined complex phasor quantity of the generator in the machine frame. Network referenced quantities (here current, I_G , and voltage V_G) are denoted

$$\begin{aligned} I_G &= I_D + jI_Q \\ V_G &= V_D + jV_Q \end{aligned}$$

in a manner similar to the machine referenced quantities, but using capital letter subscripts. The machine and network quantities are related by

$$\begin{aligned} I_D + jI_Q &= (I_d + jI_q)e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} \\ V_D + jV_Q &= (V_d + jV_q)e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} \end{aligned}$$

which is a rotation in the complex plane. The constant difference of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ is due to the fact that induction occurs perpendicular to the datum d axis.

The units used are not absolute voltage and current, but rather “per-unit” voltage and current. The per-unit system is a scaling of quantities to a reference value, described in detail in Glover et al, as well as Sauer and Pai [1, 3]. The important reference values are a base power quantity, S_B , which is generally the rated power output of the largest machine in the network, and a base voltage quantity, V_B , which is a rated RMS line-to-neutral voltage. Other base quantities, such as current, are determined from these quantities. Using the per-unit system, quantities assume a convenient range of values (≈ 1) instead of their absolute values ($\approx 100,000$).

2.1.1 The One-Axis Generator Model

The one axis generator model is a system of differential-algebraic equations relating the dynamic quantities of the generator and the algebraic relations that constrain them.

Voltage Dynamics: Voltage dynamics are the combined quantities of the exciter and it’s controller that specify the exciter reference voltage and ultimately affect

Figure 2.1: Synchronous Generator Diagram

the generator's output voltage. The first differential equation describes the dynamics of the induced EMF on the q-axis, and is given by

$$T_{do} \frac{dE_q}{dt} = -E_q - (X_d - X'_d) I_d + E_{fd} \quad (2.3)$$

where T_{do} is a time constant to scale the voltage dynamics to a common time scale, E_q is the electromotive force induced on the moving q-axis, X_d and X'_d are reactances of the stator coils scaled into the moving d-q reference frame, and E_{fd} is the voltage applied across the field coil. The dynamics of the induced EMF on the d-axis are so rapid, compared to other dynamics, that it is modeled with an algebraic equation rather than differential equation. This equation is

$$E_d = (X_q - X'_q) I_q, \quad (2.4)$$

where E_d is the voltage along the d-axis, and X_q and X'_q are reactances of the stator coils scaled into the moving d-q reference frame. This definition of an algebraic, rather than differential, relation distinguishes the one-axis model from the two-axis model where both are differential expressions. The dynamics of the voltage seen across the field coil of the rotor is given by the expression

$$T_E \frac{dE_{fd}}{dt} = -(K_E + S_e(E_{fd})) E_{fd} + V_R, \quad (2.5)$$

where K_E is the exciter constant, depending on the type of energy source for the exciter and T_E is a scaling time constant. The function $S_e(E_{fd})$ is a nonlinear function (typically exponential) which models the nonlinearity associated with magnetic iron saturation. V_R is the output of the voltage regulator, and is governed

by the differential equation

$$T_A \frac{dV_R}{dt} = -V_R + K_A(V_{ref} - V_t) \quad (2.6)$$

that models the feedback behavior of the voltage regulator, where T_A is a time scaling constant, K_A is an amplifier gain of the proportional feedback, V_{ref} is the reference voltage of the voltage regulator and one of two inputs to the system, and V_t is the voltage magnitude at the generator output (equal to $|V_G|$). The generator in the synchronous frame can be described with an equivalent circuit, defined by the stator algebraic equation

$$\left((X_q - X'_d)I_q + jE_q \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} = (R_s + jX'_d)(I_d + jI_q) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} + (V_d + jV_q) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} \quad (2.7)$$

where R_s is the stator series resistance. The machine angle δ will be defined in the mechanical dynamics below.

Mechanical Dynamics: The mechanical dynamics model a speed-governed steam turbine that supplies mechanical energy to the rotor, and the interaction between mechanical power supplied and electrical energy generated. This interaction determines acceleration of the rotor. This acceleration is the derivative of equation (2.1), and is given by the equation

$$\frac{d\delta}{dt} = \omega - \omega_s \quad (2.8)$$

which defines the rate of change of the angle δ . This angle is defined as the angular position of voltage and current phase angle with respect to the synchronous reference frame. ω is the angular speed of the rotor and ω_s is the rated synchronous frequency. The turbine model is governed by the differential equation

$$T_{CH} \frac{dT_M}{dt} = -T_M + P_{SV} \quad (2.9)$$

where T_{CH} is a time scaling constant, T_M is the mechanical power from the turbine, and P_{SV} is the steam valve position governed by the differential equation

$$T_{SV} \frac{dP_{SV}}{dt} = -P_{SV} + P_C - \frac{1}{R_D} \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_s} - 1 \right) \quad (2.10)$$

where T_{SV} is a time scaling constant, P_C is the speed governor set point, and R_D is the per-unit "droop-rate" of the governor. The governor set point is either set by local area operators, or is part of an automatic generator control (AGC) scheme, discussed in Glover et al [1]. Essentially, over or under-frequency conditions (variance from ω_s) are detected on the grid and local P_C values are changed

to correct the power imbalance. The mechanical and electrical portions of the model interact in the form of conservation of angular momentum. The acceleration of the rotor is described by the differential equation

$$M \frac{d\omega}{dt} = T_M - E_d I_d - E_q I_q - (X'_q - X'_d) I_d I_q - D(\omega - \omega_s) \quad (2.11)$$

where M is a time and mass-inertia constant of the rotor, and D is a linear model of mechanical energy loss of the system. It should be noted that the “transient saliency” assumption has been made in this thesis, and explained in Sauer and Pai [3], which is the assumption that

$$X'_d = X'_q \quad (2.12)$$

which is an assumption of symmetry of the stator coils. Making this substitution into equation (2.11) gives the simplified equation

$$M \frac{d\omega}{dt} = T_M - E_d I_d - E_q I_q - D(\omega - \omega_s) \quad (2.13)$$

These above equations (2.3-2.13) model the internal dynamics of the synchronous generator. It is the circuitry that the generator is supplying power to that determines the relationship between the generator terminal voltage and injected current.

2.1.2 Power Network: Transmission Lines and Loads

Transmission lines are essentially conductive wires for current to flow, but due to the scale of power being transmitted and their physical geometry, the parametric values associated with the lines are significant. The four electrical parameters associated with a transmission line are the series resistance R , the line-to-ground capacitance C , the line-to-line inductance L , and line-to-ground conductance G . These parameters are typically put into a model known as the “pi” model, shown in figure 2.2.

Line-to-ground conductance is typically negligible and line-to-ground capacitance is only considered in long lines. Since the current moving through the line is assumed to be at or near operating frequency at all times, the line capacitance and inductance can be considered in terms of capacitive and inductive reactances, X_C and X_L , respectively.

The admittance matrix is a square matrix that relates system voltages to system currents. It is the result of nodal analysis of the transmission lines connecting system buses, where the line’s series impedance is taken as

$$Z = R + jX_L \quad (2.14)$$

Figure 2.2: Pi Model of a Transmission Line

and line-to-ground admittance is taken as

$$\frac{Y_C}{2} = \frac{1}{2X_C}. \quad (2.15)$$

The series line admittance would then simply be

$$Y = \frac{1}{Z} = G + jB \quad (2.16)$$

The current in or out of a node k is found using node voltage equations for n buses

$$I_k = (V_k - V_1)Y_{k,1} + (V_k - V_2)Y_{k,2} + \dots + V_k Y_{k,k} + (V_k - V_n)Y_{k,n}, \quad (2.17)$$

where Y_{kk} is the shunt (bus-to-ground) admittance and Y_{kn} is the admittance between buses k and n . Arranging the equations for all currents and voltages in matrix vector form yields

$$I = YV \quad (2.18)$$

where I is a vector of currents and V is a vector of bus voltages. The matrix of admittances Y is defined by

$$Y_{ik} = \begin{cases} Y_{ik} & i \neq k \\ -\sum_{i \neq k} Y_{ik} - Y_{kk} & i = k \end{cases} \quad (2.19)$$

Where Y_{kk} is an admittance associated with the bus k , typically line charging on long lines, and could also be a representation of a load admittance at bus k .

Loads themselves and load modeling are an area of active research. Often loads are assumed to be a function of voltage, from a impedance-type V_L^2 relation to power to combinations of linear, constant and non-linear voltage dependence, as described in Kundur [2].

The overall structure of the generator and it's relations to other power system components is shown in figure 2.3. The inputs of the generators, V_{ref} and P_C , are shown in context, as well as the structure of feedback control using terminal voltage V_t to steer voltage/exciter dynamics and P_C to set desired output power.

Figure 2.3: A Block Diagram of Power System Components

2.2 Differential Flatness

Differential flatness is a geometric property of control systems, well explained in Murray et al and Lévine [9, 10]. A system $\frac{dx}{dt} = f(x, u)$ is differentially flat if there exists flat outputs y , equal in number to inputs u , such that

$$y = H(x)$$

$$u = \phi(y, \dot{y}, \dots)$$

This makes differential flatness a very useful property. If the flat outputs are specified, the functions ϕ will determine the input necessary for those outputs to occur. Such a property can be used to specify control input, or used as part of linearizing feedback. Examples can be seen in Martin and Rouchon, as well as Glass et al [11, 12].

Figure 2.4: Buck-Type DC-to-DC Converter

2.2.1 Example of Differential Flatness

An example of differential flatness is in a “buck-type” DC-to-DC converter described in Sira-Ramirez and Ilic-Spong [13] and is shown in figure 2.4. Let

$$\begin{aligned} x_1 &= I\sqrt{L} \\ x_2 &= V\sqrt{C} \\ w_0 &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{LC}} \\ w_1 &= \frac{1}{RC} \\ b &= E\sqrt{L} \end{aligned}$$

with $u = 0, 1$, the input is intended to be some form of pulse width modulation. The dynamic equations of the converter model would then be

$$\frac{dx_1}{dt} = -w_0x_2 + ub \quad (2.20)$$

$$\frac{dx_2}{dt} = w_0x_1 - w_1x_2. \quad (2.21)$$

Showing the flatness of the system in equations (2.20) and (2.21) involves finding the flat output and computing other states and inputs in terms of this flat output and its time derivatives. Inspection shows that x_2 is the flat output, which is also hinted to in [13]. Supposing that $y = x_2$ is the flat output, then from 2.21,

$$x_1 = \frac{1}{w_0} \left(w_1x_2 + \frac{dx_2}{dt} \right).$$

Differentiating

$$\dot{x}_1 = \frac{1}{w_0} \left(w_1 \frac{dx_2}{dt} + \frac{d^2x_2}{dt^2} \right)$$

from which

$$\frac{1}{bw_0} \left(w_1 \frac{dx_2}{dt} + \frac{d^2x_2}{dt^2} \right) + \frac{w_0}{b} x_2 = u$$

follows from 2.20 such that the input of the converter is given in terms of it's flat output x_2 .

CHAPTER 3

FLATNESS OF THE GENERATOR MODEL

The process of showing differential flatness is to compute all dynamic variables (states) and control inputs in terms of flat outputs. Flat outputs are not unique, as described in Lévine [10], but for the purposes of this thesis, the network-frame currents I_D and I_Q will be chosen. In the following computations, these currents and their derivatives with respect to time are assumed to be known.

The key to showing differential flatness is to relate the network-frame voltages and the network-frame currents. Terminal voltages and currents could be related in such a way by measurements, but the voltages and currents can also be related by some equivalent impedance

$$(V_D + jV_Q) = Z_{eq}(I_D + jI_Q). \quad (3.1)$$

Starting with the stator algebraic equation (2.7)

$$\left((X_q - X'_q)I_q + jE_q \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} = V_t e^{j\theta} + (R_s + jX'_d)(I_d + jI_q) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})},$$

and substituting equation 3.1,

$$\left((X_q - X'_q)I_q + jE_q \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} = Z_{eq}(I_D + jI_Q) + (R_s + jX'_d)(I_d + jI_q) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})},$$

followed by multiplying reactances through and moving terms over from the right hand side yields

$$\left((X_q - X'_q)I_q + jE_q - jX'_d(I_d + jI_q) \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} = Z_{eq}(I_D + jI_Q) + R_s e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})}. \quad (3.2)$$

Showing only the left hand side for convenience

$$= \left(X_q I_q - X'_q I_q + jE_q - jX'_d I_d + X'_d I_q \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})}$$

and canceling terms under the saliency assumption in definition (2.12), the left hand side becomes

$$= \left(X_q I_q + jE_q - jX'_d I_d \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})}. \quad (3.3)$$

Continued manipulation of the left hand side of equation (3.3) by adding and subtracting $jX_q I_d$ yields

$$= \left(X_q I_q + jE_q - jX'_d I_d + jX_q I_d - jX_q I_d \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})}$$

and collecting terms yields

$$= \left(X_q (I_q - jI_d) + jE_q + j(X_q - X'_d) I_d \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})}$$

which can be rewritten as

$$= \left(-jX_q (I_d + jI_q) + jE_q + j(X_q - X'_d) I_d \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})}. \quad (3.4)$$

Using this left hand side and moving terms back to the right hand side of equation (3.2),

$$\left(jE_q + j(X_q - X'_d) I_d \right) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} = Z_{eq} (I_D + jI_Q) + (R_s + jX_q) (I_d + jI_q) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})}$$

simplifies to

$$\left((X_q - X'_d) I_d + E_q \right) e^{j(\delta)} = Z_{eq} (I_D + jI_Q) + (R_s + jX_q) (I_D + jI_Q).$$

Let

$$\hat{\Psi} = Z_{eq} (I_D + jI_Q) + (R_s + jX_q) (I_D + jI_Q) = \Psi (I_D, I_Q)$$

be a complex quantity in terms of I_D and I_Q . Importantly, note that δ can be computed from the angle of this complex quantity, via

$$\delta = \text{angle}(\hat{\Psi}) = \delta(I_D, I_Q). \quad (3.5)$$

The machine frame currents can therefore be determined by

$$(I_d + jI_q) = (I_D + jI_Q) e^{-j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})}$$

and the magnitude of the complex quantity Ψ can be used to compute the quadrature axis voltage through

$$(X_q - X'_d) I_d + E_q = |\hat{\Psi}|, \quad (3.6)$$

$$E_q = |\hat{\Psi}| - (X_q - X'_d) I_d = E_q(I_D, I_Q).$$

Differentiating E_q yields

$$\frac{dE_q}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left[|\hat{\Psi}| - (X_q - X'_d) I_d \right]. \quad (3.7)$$

If \dot{E}_q , E_q , and I_d are known in terms of flat outputs, then substituting into equation (2.3) to compute E_{fd} yields

$$E_{fd} = T_{do} \frac{dE_q}{dt} + E_q + (X_d - X'_d) I_d \quad (3.8)$$

and differentiating then yields

$$\frac{dE_{fd}}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left[T_{do} \frac{dE_q}{dt} + E_q + (X_d - X'_d) I_d \right].$$

With \dot{E}_{fd} and E_{fd} known in terms of flat outputs, they can be substituted into equation (2.5) to compute V_R

$$V_R = T_E \frac{dE_{fd}}{dt} + (K_E + S_e(E_{fd})) E_{fd} \quad (3.9)$$

and differentiating

$$\frac{dV_R}{dt} = T_E \frac{d^2 E_{fd}}{dt^2} + K_E \frac{dE_{fd}}{dt} + S_e(E_{fd}) \frac{dE_{fd}}{dt} + E_{fd} \frac{d}{dt} (S_e(E_{fd})). \quad (3.10)$$

Substituting into equation (2.6)

$$V_{ref} = \frac{1}{K_A} \left(T_A \frac{dV_R}{dt} + V_R + K_A V_t \right) \quad (3.11)$$

which yields V_{ref} , the first control input.

With δ calculated in terms of flat outputs, $\dot{\delta}$, $\ddot{\delta}$, and $\dddot{\delta}$ can be calculated directly through differentiation. Substituting $\dot{\delta}$ directly into equation (2.8) yields

$$\dot{\delta} = \omega - \omega_s \quad (3.12)$$

or

$$\omega = \dot{\delta} + \omega_s$$

which gives ω in terms of the flat outputs. With higher derivatives of δ computed, then it is trivially found that

$$\dot{\omega} = \ddot{\delta} \quad (3.13)$$

and

$$\ddot{\omega} = \dddot{\delta}. \quad (3.14)$$

Substituting equations (3.13) and (3.12) into equation (2.13) gives

$$M\ddot{\delta} = T_M - E_d I_d - E_q I_q - D(\dot{\delta})$$

and using equation (2.4), T_M can be calculated in terms of flat output as

$$T_M = M\ddot{\delta} + (X_q - X'_q) I_q I_d + E_q I_q + D(\dot{\delta}). \quad (3.15)$$

Differentiating,

$$\frac{dT_M}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left[M\ddot{\delta} + (X_q - X'_q) I_q I_d + E_q I_q + D(\dot{\delta}) \right] \quad (3.16)$$

and finally, substituting into equation (2.9) to solve for P_{SV} gives

$$P_{SV} = T_{CH} \frac{dT_M}{dt} + T_M. \quad (3.17)$$

Differentiating,

$$\frac{dP_{SV}}{dt} = T_{CH} \frac{d^2 T_M}{dt^2} + \frac{dT_M}{dt} \quad (3.18)$$

and substituting into equation (2.10) gives

$$P_C = T_{SV} \frac{dP_{SV}}{dt} + P_{SV} + \frac{1}{R_D} \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_s} - 1 \right),$$

or,

$$P_C = T_{SV} \frac{dP_{SV}}{dt} + P_{SV} + \frac{1}{R_D} \left(\frac{\dot{\delta}}{\omega_s} \right), \quad (3.19)$$

yielding our second control input P_C .

This shows that the generator model is flat under the assumption that terminal voltages can be determined from injected currents. The only appreciable difference between flatness of a single generator and a system of n-generators is that each generator's inputs are algebraically coupled to the injected current of every generator and load by definition (2.18).

CHAPTER 4

OPEN-LOOP CONTROL OF THE SMIB SYSTEM

With the flatness property demonstrated in the previous chapter, a simple application of the property can be demonstrated. One of the basic results of differential flatness is that if the flat outputs (and their derivatives) are specified as functions of time, then the inputs for such an output are automatically computed. This method will be demonstrated on the Single-Machine Infinite-Bus (SMIB) system, shown in figure 4.1.

The loadflow equations of the SMIB system are found by loop analysis of the equivalent circuit in figure 4.1 and are given by

$$(R_e + jX_e) (I_d + jI_q) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} + V_\infty e^{j\theta_\infty} = (V_d + jV_q) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})},$$

The injected currents can be isolated as

$$(I_d + jI_q) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} = \frac{(V_d + jV_q) e^{j(\delta - \frac{\pi}{2})} - V_\infty e^{j\theta_\infty}}{R_e + jX_e}.$$

In the case of the one-axis generator model, if we define the output network currents $I_D + jI_Q$ as well as sufficiently many of their derivatives, then the control inputs P_C and V_{ref} will be calculated. This overall control scheme is shown in figure 4.2.

As an example of the trajectory generation abilities that differential flatness provides, the generator will be guided from its initial steady state operating point to a new steady state operating point. The requirement that flatness puts on this, however, is that we must define the first four derivatives of whatever function we choose to interpolate between these two steady states. Care must also be taken in that P_{SV} and V_R have physical limits as well as the fact that our chosen trajectories for I_D and I_Q must be physically meaningful as part of a current balance loadflow, described in Sauer and Pai [3], as well.

4.1 Trajectory Generation

The chosen method for creating a sufficiently smooth trajectory between steady state values is polynomial interpolation. Polynomials are used due to the

fact that they are smooth over their domain, can be fit to achieve most any realistic control objective, and are trivial to differentiate. The process of calculating these polynomials is discussed in Appendix B.

With the output currents specified, they can be substituted into the equations of the previous chapter. Shown in a functional form of

$$P_C = \phi_1(I_D, I_Q, \dot{I}_D, \dot{I}_Q, \dots) \quad (4.1)$$

and

$$V_{ref} = \phi_2(I_D, I_Q, \dot{I}_D, \dot{I}_Q, \dots). \quad (4.2)$$

4.2 Simulation Results

A simulation was run using the above method of open loop trajectory generation. Steady state currents were calculated via corresponding terminal voltages, $V_t e^{j\theta}$, in the infinite bus model of $V_1 = 1.05e^{j0^\circ} pu$ and $V_2 = 1.00e^{j5^\circ} pu$. Letting $R_e = 0.032\Omega pu$ and $X_e = 0.161\Omega pu$, this gives the two steady state currents

$$I_{D_1} + jI_{Q_1} = 0.0593 - j0.2987 \quad (4.3)$$

and

$$I_{D_2} + jI_{Q_2} = 0.5145 + j0.1320 \quad (4.4)$$

A polynomial was then calculated to move between these steady states, beginning at $t = 10.0$ and finishing at $t = 30.0$. The system is then solved using GNU Octave's [14] **daspk** DAE solver. The result of this simulation is in Figure 4.3.

The inputs P_C and V_{ref} used to generate these currents are in figures 4.4 and 4.5, respectively. Figure 4.3 shows that the resulting trajectories from a SMIB system with generator modeled by equations (2.3)-(2.13) match the desired trajectories. The corresponding inputs to accomplish this show that the inputs required to achieve the outputs in Figure 4.3 are reasonable.

Figure 4.1: Single Machine Infinite Bus

Figure 4.2: Open-Loop Control Scheme

Figure 4.3: Desired and Resulting Real and Imaginary Injected Current

Figure 4.4: P_C Generated for Open-Loop SMIB Control

Figure 4.5: V_{ref} Generated for Open-Loop SMIB Control

CHAPTER 5

LINEARIZING FEEDBACK OF A 9-BUS SYSTEM

The open-loop control method of the previous chapter shows a straightforward and very powerful application of the flatness property. Open loop control, however, is not a robust control strategy. Feedback control can compensate for uncertainties and disturbances in the system, which cannot be done automatically by open loop control. An application of differential flatness to feedback control is to use the flatness property to handle the nonlinearities of the system as part of a standard feedback scheme.

5.1 The 9-Bus System with Constant Impedance-Type Loads

This linearizing feedback scheme is applied to a 9-bus system that includes three generators and three constant impedance type loads. A one-line diagram of this system is shown in figure 5.1.

This system is identical to the multi-machine system used in Sauer and Pai [3] with the exception that buses have been relabeled to group generators and loads.

5.1.1 Line Impedances

The line admittances connecting the buses are listed in table 5.1. The network model also includes line charging due to line length. These charging admittances appear on the main diagonal of the admittance matrix and are listed in table 5.2.

5.1.2 Constant Impedance Loads

The system under study has constant impedance type loads. These load impedances are directly computed by taking the ratio of bus voltage and current computed from a load-flow solution. These calculated impedances are shown in

i,j	Y_{ij}
4,1	$0+j17.361$
6,2	$0+j16$
5,3	$0+j17.065$
9,4	$-1.3652+j11.604$
7,4	$-1.9422+j10.511$
6,9	$-1.1876+j5.9751$
8,6	$-1.6171+j13.698$
5,8	$-1.1551+j9.7843$
7,5	$-1.282+j5.5882$

Table 5.1: 9-Bus Admittance Matrix Line Components

bus (j)	Y_{jj}
4	$j0.16700$
5	$j0.28350$
6	$j0.22750$
7	$j0.25800$
8	$j0.17900$
9	$j0.24100$

Table 5.2: 9-Bus Admittance Matrix Line-Charging Components

bus (j)	Y_{jj}
7	$-0.885 + j0.284$
8	$-0.981 + j0.334$
9	$-1.265 + j0.5$

Table 5.3: 9-Bus Admittance Matrix Load Components

Figure 5.1: One-line Diagram of the 9-Bus System

table 5.3. The constant loads can be used in Ward reduction to reduce the entire system to be composed of the three generators, the equivalent loads connected to the generators, and the admittances coupling the generators. Using the methods in Appendix A and the above data, the equivalent admittance matrix is computed to be

$$Y_{eq} = \begin{pmatrix} 1.1092 - j4.6932 & 0.0988 + j2.2582 & 0.0071 + j2.2764 \\ 0.0988 + j2.2582 & 0.7389 - j5.1132 & 0.1260 + j2.8267 \\ 0.0071 + j2.2764 & 0.1260 + j2.8267 & 0.7244 - j5.0219 \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.1)$$

where the equivalent network and loads connected to buses 1, 2, and 3 has been found.

5.2 Flatness-based Linearizing Feedback

The task of any linearizing control scheme is to use control methods, typically feedback methods, to make the combination of the control and system dynamics to be linear in behavior. A typical method is to use a linearization around a desired operating point of the system. This method, as well as other methods, is discussed in Sontag [5]. Differential flatness can be used in a linearizing feedback scheme by using the flat relationship between the flat outputs and system dynamics to cancel out or negate nonlinear behavior. This method involves first using the same methods in Chapter 3 to calculate control input given flat outputs,

with the exception of the last step

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{P}_{SV} \\ P_{SV} \end{bmatrix} = \phi_1(I_D, I_Q, \dot{I}_D, \dot{I}_Q, \dots) \quad (5.2)$$

and

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{V}_R \\ V_R \end{bmatrix} = \phi_2(I_D, I_Q, \dot{I}_D, \dot{I}_Q, \dots). \quad (5.3)$$

It should also be noted that since the load admittances are constant, then the condition in equation (3.1) is valid and the equivalent impedance matrix Z_{eq} is a constant, allowing for straightforward differentiation.

Given a desired trajectory of I_D, I_Q , these functions can be used to compute desired dynamics

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{P}_{SV_d} \\ P_{SV_d} \end{bmatrix} = \phi_1(I_{D_d}, I_{Q_d}, \dot{I}_{D_d}, \dot{I}_{Q_d}, \dots)$$

and

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{V}_{R_d} \\ V_{R_d} \end{bmatrix} = \phi_2(I_{D_d}, I_{Q_d}, \dot{I}_{D_d}, \dot{I}_{Q_d}, \dots).$$

Such functions could be used to create control functions

$$V_{ref} = \frac{1}{K_A} \left(T_A \frac{dV_{R_d}}{dt} + V_{R_d} + K_A V_t \right) \quad (5.4)$$

and

$$P_C = T_{SV} \frac{dP_{SV_d}}{dt} + P_{SV_d} + \frac{1}{R_D} \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_s} - 1 \right) \quad (5.5)$$

to which proportional terms can be added to make feedback control functions

$$V_{ref} = \frac{1}{K_A} \left(T_A \frac{dV_{R_d}}{dt} + V_R + K_A V_t + \lambda_1 (V_{R_d} - V_R) \right) \quad (5.6)$$

and

$$P_C = T_{SV} \frac{dP_{SV_d}}{dt} + P_{SV} + \frac{1}{R_D} \left(\frac{\omega}{\omega_s} - 1 \right) + \lambda_2 (P_{SV_d} - P_{SV}). \quad (5.7)$$

Where λ_1 and λ_2 are the proportional gain terms. The overall control structure is shown in figure 5.2.

Substituting equation (5.6) and equation(5.7) into equation (2.6) and equation (2.10), respectively, the result

$$T_A \frac{dV_R}{dt} = -V_R + K_A \left(\left[\frac{1}{K_A} \left(T_A \frac{dV_{R_d}}{dt} + V_R + K_A V_t + \lambda_1 (V_{R_d} - V_R) \right) \right] - V_t \right)$$

Figure 5.2: Closed-Loop Control Scheme for The Linearizing Feedback

or

$$0 = T_A \left(\frac{dV_{R_d}}{dt} - \frac{dV_R}{dt} \right) + \lambda_1 (V_{R_d} - V_R). \quad (5.8)$$

Similarly,

$$0 = T_{SV} \left(\frac{dP_{SV_d}}{dt} - \frac{dP_{SV}}{dt} \right) + \lambda_2 (P_{SV_d} - P_{SV}). \quad (5.9)$$

If we define an error term to be

$$\begin{pmatrix} V_{R_{err}} \\ P_{SV_{err}} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} V_{R_d} \\ P_{SV_d} \end{pmatrix} - \begin{pmatrix} V_R \\ P_{SV} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.10)$$

Considering equation (5.8) and equation (5.9) in terms of such error dynamics

$$\vec{0} = \begin{pmatrix} T_A & 0 \\ 0 & T_{SV} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{dV_{R_{err}}}{dt} \\ \frac{dP_{SV_{err}}}{dt} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \lambda_1 V_{R_{err}} \\ \lambda_2 P_{SV_{err}} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.11)$$

which has solutions of

$$V_{R_{err}} = V_{R_{err0}} e^{-\frac{\lambda_1}{T_A} t} \quad (5.12)$$

and

$$P_{SV_{err}} = P_{SV_{err0}} e^{-\frac{\lambda_2}{T_{SV}} t} \quad (5.13)$$

for all initial conditions. These error dynamics will therefore exponentially converge to zero.

5.2.1 Control Objective

As a demonstration of multi-machine coordination using linearizing feedback, polynomial perturbation functions will be used to generate a smooth desired trajectory. A polynomial perturbation function is similar to the steady state to steady state polynomial interpolation as used previously and discussed in Appendix B, only a second interpolation returns the system to it's original steady state. The control objective is to apply a perturbation function to generator 1's controller, as well as an appropriately scaled perturbation to generator 3's controller, such that generator 2 is in steady state for the whole operation. To calculate this appropriate scale suppose that I_{G_Δ} is the maximum of a perturbation function.

In a multi-machine, multi-load setting, the current-voltage relationship in a network is defined by the matrix vector equation (2.18). This model of impedance type loads and transmission lines can be reduced down to an equivalent circuit model described in Ward, as well as Baldwin et al [15, 16]. The relation between generator voltages and currents can be described as

$$I_G = Y_{eq} V_G \quad (5.14)$$

where Y_{eq} is the equivalent admittance matrix. The calculation of Y_{eq} is shown in Appendix A. Inversion of the matrix into an impedance matrix, Z_{eq} , will enable the generator terminal voltages to be written as a function of injected network currents.

$$V_G = Y_{eq}^{-1} I_G = Z_{eq} I_G \quad (5.15)$$

Then when the currents are to be perturbed away from this steady state

$$V_{G_0} + V_{G_\Delta} = Z_{eq}(I_{G_0} + I_{G_\Delta}) \quad (5.16)$$

or

$$V_{G_\Delta} = Z_{eq} I_{G_\Delta} \quad (5.17)$$

For the system in figure 5.1, Z_{eq} is a 3x3 matrix.

$$\begin{bmatrix} V_{G_{\Delta 1}} \\ V_{G_{\Delta 2}} \\ V_{G_{\Delta 3}} \end{bmatrix} = [Z_{eq}] \begin{bmatrix} I_{G_{\Delta 1}} \\ I_{G_{\Delta 2}} \\ I_{G_{\Delta 3}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5.18)$$

The conditions for $V_{G_{\Delta 2}}$ to be zero are

$$I_{G_{\Delta 2}} = 0 \quad (5.19)$$

and

$$I_{G_{\Delta 3}} = -\frac{Z_{2,1}}{Z_{2,3}} I_{G_{\Delta 1}} \quad (5.20)$$

which follows from equation (5.18). This shows that voltage objectives can be used to specify current trajectories.

The initial data, I_{G_0} and V_{G_0} , for the simulation is given in table 5.4. The perturbation for generator 1 in this example is $I_{G_{\Delta 1}} = 0.3 - j0.2$. The operation will begin at $t = 10.0$, reach peak at $t = 20.0$, and end at $t = 30.0$.

bus	V_0	I_0	S_0
1	1.0402 - j0.0000	0.6877 - j0.2611	0.7154 + j0.2715
2	1.0117 + j0.1651	1.5780 + j0.1918	1.6282 + j0.0664
3	1.0214 + j0.0838	0.8205 + j0.1750	0.8527 - j0.1100
4	1.0251 - j0.0397	0	0
5	1.0317 + j0.0357	0	0
6	1.0237 + j0.0665	0	0
7	1.0106 - j0.0650	-0.8678 + j0.3526	-0.8999 - j0.2999
8	1.0158 + j0.0130	-0.9886 + j0.3318	-0.9999 - j0.3499
9	0.9933 - j0.0692	-1.2173 + j0.5882	-1.2500 - j0.4999

Table 5.4: 9-Bus Initial System Data

5.3 Simulation Results

The results of the control objective are shown in figure 5.3 and figure 5.4. Generators 1 and 3 are steered away from steady state in such a way that generator 2 is left in steady state. Again, GNU Octave's **daspk** was used.

This control method shows that flatness can be adapted to a linearizing feedback scheme in each generator, as well as showing that voltage objectives can be used, along with Ward equivalents, to specify the desired current trajectories.

Figure 5.3: Real Generator Currents due to 9-Bus Linearizing Feedback

Figure 5.4: Imaginary Generator Currents due to 9-Bus Linearizing Feedback

CHAPTER 6

CONTROL OF 9-BUS SYSTEM WITH TIME-VARYING DEMAND

The main purpose of active control of power generation is to match generation of power to power consumption at the loads. The transmission system connecting the generators and loads determines much of the participation of each generator in satisfying load demand. This chapter outlines a method for the network parameters to determine generator currents, given the load voltages and currents. Typically, load power is modeled entirely as a function of load voltage, as described in Kundur et. al. [2], but for the sake of generality, it will be assumed here that both voltage and current are measured. The loads used in this example are again an impedance type, but will also have a series current source that will vary with time. An equivalent circuit of this load model is shown in figure 6.1.

The 9-bus system of the previous chapter is again explored with this varying power demand. Ward reduction techniques will be used to calculate the required generator voltage and current, given the "measured" load voltage and current. In a realistic system, measurements would not be directly used in a control loop. An area generator control system would take into account both variations in measured voltages and currents, as well as variations in frequency and scheduled inter-area power transfers, described in Glover et al and Kundur [1, 2].

In the time-varying load model, the load currents vary independently in time. The currents are varied using a steady state interpolating polynomial as described in Appendix B. The polynomial movement begins at time $t = 10$ and ends at time $t = 40$.

The results of simulations are shown for both generators where the control inputs are fixed, as to demonstrate the degenerate behavior that would ensue, and where the voltages and currents of the loads determine the desired genera-

bus	I_1	I_2
7	$-0.8678 + j0.3526$	$-0.8878 + j0.3026$
8	$-0.9886 + j0.3318$	$-0.9986 + j0.3418$
9	$-1.2173 + j0.5882$	$-1.2173 + j0.5882$

Table 6.1: Load Current Steady State Values

Figure 6.1: Time-Varying Load Model

tor currents and voltages, which are used as input to the input-generating flat functions.

6.1 Constant Control Results

Figures 6.3-6.6 show effects of a time-varying load profile in the 9-bus system shown in figure 5.1. In this simulation, there is no compensation for change in current in the load, leading to fall in voltage magnitude and chronic angular drift. These plots show the degenerating condition of unbalanced conditions in the generator dynamics. In large systems, voltage swings during changes in operating conditions can contribute to voltage instability related issues such as under-voltage conditions or angular instability, explained in Kundur et al [4].

6.2 Feedback Controlled Results

In order to compensate for disturbance and variation of power demand, the operating conditions of the generator must be adjusted. For flatness-based methods to be used, the desired generator currents and several of their time derivatives must be determined through load voltages and currents. The Ward reduction techniques used are described in Appendix A. The Ward algebra is used to calculate required I_D and I_Q given load voltages and currents. These desired currents are directly into equations (3.11) and (3.19). Figures 6.7-6.10 show system dynamics resulting from the feedback method shown in figure 6. The generator dynamics show recovery of both voltage magnitude and angle to new

steady state conditions. The key contribution of the flatness based control is coordination of reactive power output with demand, which gives the angular stability necessary to avoid many forms of power system instability.

Figure 6.2: Feedback Control Scheme

Figure 6.3: 9-Bus Terminal Voltage Magnitude: Constant Control

Figure 6.4: 9-Bus Terminal Voltage Angle: Constant Control

Figure 6.5: 9-Bus Terminal Real Current: Constant Control

Figure 6.6: 9-Bus Terminal Reactive Current: Constant Control

Figure 6.7: 9-Bus Terminal Voltage Magnitude: Feedback Control

Figure 6.8: 9-Bus Terminal Voltage Angle: Feedback Control

Figure 6.9: 9-Bus Terminal Real Current: Feedback Control

Figure 6.10: 9-Bus Terminal Imaginary Current: Feedback Control

CHAPTER 7

EFFECTS OF ERROR IN MODEL AND PARAMETERS

The obvious barrier between flatness-based techniques and practical implementation is the complete knowledge of the model and its parameters. Clearly, if there is any error in the structure of the model or its parameters as used by the inverting flat functions, then the computed control values will be in error as a result. The following sections summarize a study as to how assumptions in the model and errors in parameters impact the input-computing functions and ultimately the model's response to these inputs. Studies done in this chapter will be performed on the SMIB system in figure 4.1 and will use the same open-loop planned trajectory as used in chapter 4. The effects of model error, in the form of differential, rather than algebraic, relations for E_d will be presented. The effects of erroneous parameter values used in the trajectory planning functions will then be explored using a sensitivity analysis.

7.1 Model Error

The model presented in equations (2.3)-(2.13) in chapter 2 for which the property of flatness that was shown in chapter 3, is known as the "one-axis" or "flux-decay" model and is based on the model developed in Sauer and Pai [3]. This model is distinguished from the "two-axis" model where E_d in equation (2.4) is defined instead by a differential equation.

$$T_{qo} \frac{dE_d}{dt} = -E_d + (X_q - X'_q) I_q \quad (7.1)$$

The algebraic approximation of equation (7.1) that results in equation (2.4) is due to the fact that $T_{qo} \ll T_{do}$, meaning the dynamic behavior of E_d is qualitatively much faster than E_q . The modeling approximation is to have E_d as a steady state solution of the differential equation (7.1), since the dynamics of the equation are assumed to reach steady state long before the voltage dynamics of equation (2.3) have reached their own steady state.

An additional modeling approximation was made to the voltage dynamics in equations (2.3)-(2.7) that resulted in "fast exciter dynamics". Similar to the direct-axis dynamics and simplification above, the dynamic behavior of the voltage exciter was assumed to be "fast" with respect to other dynamics and were

modeled with algebraic, rather than differential equations. More detailed modeling of exciter dynamics involve a "rate feedback" state R_f , presented in Sauer and Pai [3] as

$$T_F \frac{dR_f}{dt} = -R_f + \frac{K_F}{T_F} E_{fd}, \quad (7.2)$$

which appears in the following voltage regulator equation that was approximated by equation (2.6)

$$T_A \frac{dV_R}{dt} = -V_R + K_A R_F - \frac{K_A K_F}{T_F} E_{fd} + K_A (V_{ref} - V_t). \quad (7.3)$$

The simplified equation (2.6) used in this thesis is found by assuming "fast" rate feedback in equation (7.2), making the equation into an algebraic equation. Clearly, if the derivative in equation (7.2) is equal to zero, then substitution into equation (7.3) is precisely equal to equation (2.6).

The effects of using the functions of chapter 3, which were developed around the one-axis model with fast exciter dynamics, on a two-axis system will be investigated. The two-axis model is developed in detail in Sauer and Pai [3]. The system can be expected to deliver correct steady-state input, as the models are identical under steady-state. A simulation was done where the SMIB system was simulated with the generator represented by the two-axis model and open-loop control was given, similar to that used in chapter 4 using the same trajectory planning methods. The resulting error in the flat outputs is shown in figure 7.1.

Figure 7.1 shows that the imaginary current output is far more sensitive to one-axis dynamics and fast-exciter modeling assumptions. This can suggest investigation into flatness of models with higher detail, or less demanding changes in reactive current.

7.2 Parameter Error

Parametric error is where the value of a parameter used in the flatness function differs from the true value in the system or system model. Many parameters in the one-axis model correspond to true physical values, such as stator resistance R_s , but others are parameters used to scale the system to a common time reference, such as M . A series of simulations were performed with each simulation having open-loop control data given by flat-functions with a parameter in error. The sensitivity of the error to the change in the parameter is similar to that used in the "parameter ranking" in Hiskens and Alseddiqui [17]. This sensitivity is defined by the equation

$$S_k = \frac{\partial y(t)}{\partial \lambda_k} \quad (7.4)$$

Figure 7.1: Error in Flat Outputs due to SMIB Modeling Error

where $y(t)$ is the trajectory in question, λ_k is the k -th parameter, and S_k is the sensitivity of the trajectory to the k -th parameter. In practical computation, equation (7.4) is implemented as

$$S_k = \frac{y(\lambda + \epsilon\lambda) - y(\lambda)}{\epsilon\lambda} \quad (7.5)$$

where $\epsilon\lambda$ is the error introduced to the parameter. In the simulations done in this thesis, ϵ was taken to be 0.01, corresponding to a 1% error in the parameter. The same open-loop control simulation of chapter 4 was then performed several times, with each simulation having a parameter error in the flatness functions. The sensitivities of these simulations for a set of parameters are shown in figures 7.2-7.5.

Figures 7.2-7.5 show the relative sensitivities during the open-loop control operation. The system would appear to be highly sensitive to some parameters, such as K_E , but relatively insensitive to others, such as D or M . Fortunately, many of the more sensitive parameters are directly measurable (such as R_s) or are specified by the generator designers (such as K_A). Parameters that are combinations of physical values and time scaling for modeling convenience (such as M) are relatively insensitive.

Figure 7.2: SMIB Trajectory Sensitivities: Real Current (1)

Figure 7.3: SMIB Trajectory Sensitivities: Real Current (2)

Figure 7.4: SMIB Trajectory Sensitivities: Imaginary Current (1)

Figure 7.5: SMIB Trajectory Sensitivities: Imaginary Current (2)

CHAPTER 8

CONCLUSION

This thesis has shown the differential flatness property of a generator's dynamic model and demonstrated some applications of the property. The network-frame output current of the generator was found to be the flat output of the one-axis generator model with corresponding inputs of the exciter reference voltage and governor set-point. The flatness property was used to generate open loop control signals, perform linearizing feedback control of individual generators, and facilitate feedback control of a test power system.

Open loop control was achieved in the Single-Machine Infinite-Bus (SMIB) system where the system was steered between two steady state conditions based on a polynomial interpolation between the two, using the trajectory generating functions to create control inputs. The system identically followed the desired trajectory while keeping control limits within physical limits. Linearizing feedback was then applied to the three generators in the 9-bus test system. The system featured constant impedance-type loads, allowing the generators to be coordinated based on an equivalent circuit of the power system. The linearizing controllers and circuit simplifications allowed the first and third generator to change power output in such a way that the second generator was in steady state for the whole operation. Finally, a system-wide feedback scheme was implemented in the 9-bus system with measurements of the load voltages and currents determining the required currents from the generators, and flatness functions then determined the control inputs to match load demand.

The error due to using the one-axis model-based flatness methods in the two-axis, higher order model was explored. The error due to modeling assumptions did not affect the steady state behavior of the system, and the error during dynamic portions of operation were bounded. Sensitivity to parametric error was explored via trajectory sensitivities. Parameters were given a 1% error inside the flatness functions, and the proportionate error on the flat outputs computed. The sensitivity analysis shows which parameters must be known with high confidence before flatness methods can be used as well as those that affect transient versus steady-state tracking error.

Flatness can be a powerful tool for generator control. Power generators still must obey physical limitations, but flatness can provide control over the nonlinear dynamics of generators. Combined with accurate knowledge of the power network and detailed load modeling or measurements, greater multi-area

coordination of generators as well as system performance can be improved.

APPENDIX A

DERIVATION OF WARD EQUIVALENTS

Ward reduction is the procedure of projecting voltages, currents, and impedances from an area where details are not of interest, to a smaller set of buses that represent an area of interest.

A.1 Two-Section Ward Equivalent

The simplest application of Ward reduction is to divide a system into two areas. These two areas are labeled as a generator (G) area, where the buses are retained, and a load (L) area, where the network and loads are abstracted away. This type of study can be used in generator control studies to abstract away transmission and load components into a equivalent system. In quasi-sinusoidal-steady-state, the network's current balance equations can be written as

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_G \\ I_L \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Y_{GG} & Y_{GL} \\ Y_{LG} & Y_{LL} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} V_G \\ V_L \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where V_G and I_G are the generator voltages and currents, respectively. The load/network voltages and currents are respectively given by V_L and I_L . The block matrices Y_{GG} and Y_{LL} are square, and the matrices Y_{GL} and Y_{LG} are not necessarily square and, for the purposes of this thesis, are transposes of each other. Note that the diagonal components of the admittance matrices are square matrix blocks, equal in dimension to their corresponding generator or load vectors. Suppose the loads were modeled by some impedance or admittance. This would allow definition of a diagonal matrix Y_L such that

$$I_L = Y_L V_L \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where Y_L has diagonal components containing the admittance relating each voltage and current. The above equation is substituted into equation (A.1), giving

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_G \\ Y_L V_L \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Y_{GG} & Y_{GL} \\ Y_{LG} & Y_{LL} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} V_G \\ V_L \end{pmatrix}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Expanding equation (A.3) into the two corresponding vector equations

$$I_G = Y_{GG} V_G + Y_{GL} V_L \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Figure A.1: Reduction of 9-bus System to Equivalent 3-bus

$$Y_L V_L = Y_{LG} V_G + Y_{LL} V_L \quad (\text{A.5})$$

and using equation (A.5) to isolate V_L , which is substituted into equation (A.4), yielding

$$V_L = (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG} V_G \quad (\text{A.6})$$

and

$$I_G = Y_{GG} V_G + Y_{GL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG} V_G. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

If we now define Y_{eq} as

$$Y_{eq} = Y_{GG} + Y_{GL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

then Y_{eq} is the equivalent admittance matrix of the equivalent loads connected to the generator buses, as well as the equivalent admittances of lines connecting the generators together. This is demonstrated in figure A.1, where generators connected to buses 1-3 and load buses 4-9 are simplified into a equivalent 3-bus system.

A.2 Three-Section Ward Equivalent

It may be necessary to consider three sections of the grid. Transmission (T) buses do not contribute to loading, as they serve as connection buses, so net current through them is zero. A three-section network's current balance can be described with the system of equations

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_G \\ 0 \\ I_L \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Y_{GG} & Y_{GT} & Y_{GL} \\ Y_{TG} & Y_{TT} & Y_{TL} \\ Y_{LG} & Y_{LT} & Y_{LL} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} V_G \\ V_T \\ V_L \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

where the admittance matrix is now divided to become a 3x3 block matrix. We again define a diagonal matrix Y_L such that each diagonal entry corresponds to a equivalent admittance of each load bus.

$$Y_L V_L = I_L. \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Substituting equation (A.10) into the expanded row of equation (A.9) yields

$$Y_L V_L = Y_{LG} V_G + Y_{LT} V_T + Y_{LL} V_L. \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Solving equation (A.11) for load voltages,

$$-Y_{LG} V_G - Y_{LT} V_T = (Y_{LL} - Y_L) V_L \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$V_L = (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} [Y_{LG} V_G + Y_{LT} V_T]. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Substituting equation (A.13) into equation (A.9) and solving for V_T is as follows

$$0 = Y_{TG} V_G + Y_{TT} V_T + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} [Y_{LG} V_G + Y_{LT} V_T] \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$= [Y_{TG} + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG}] V_G + [Y_{TT} + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LT}] V_T \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$[-Y_{TT} - Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LT}] V_T = [Y_{TG} + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG}] V_G \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$V_T = [-Y_{TT} - Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LT}]^{-1} [Y_{TG} + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG}] V_G. \quad (\text{A.17})$$

V_L can now be found by substituting equation (A.17) into equation (A.13) as follows

$$V_L = (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} \left[Y_{LG} + Y_{LT} \left(-Y_{TT} - Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LT} \right)^{-1} \cdot \left(Y_{TG} + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG} \right) \right] V_G. \quad (\text{A.18})$$

Taking the first row of equation (A.9) and solving for I_G in terms of V_G using equation (A.17) and equation (A.18), yields

$$I_G = Y_{GG} V_G + Y_{GT} V_T + Y_{GL} V_L,$$

from which it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
I_G = & Y_{GG}V_G + Y_{GT} \left(\left[-Y_{TT} - Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LT} \right]^{-1} \cdot \right. \\
& \cdot \left. \left[Y_{TG} + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG} \right] \right) V_G + Y_{GL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} \cdot \\
& \cdot \left[Y_{LG} + Y_{LT} \left(-Y_{TT} - Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LT} \right)^{-1} \cdot \right. \\
& \left. \cdot \left(Y_{TG} + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG} \right) \right] V_G. \quad (\text{A.19})
\end{aligned}$$

Defining Y_{eq} as

$$\begin{aligned}
Y_{eq} = & Y_{GG} + Y_{GT} \left(\left[-Y_{TT} - Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LT} \right]^{-1} \cdot \right. \\
& \cdot \left. \left[Y_{TG} + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG} \right] \right) + Y_{GL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} \left[Y_{LG} + \right. \\
& \left. + Y_{LT} \left(-Y_{TT} - Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LT} \right)^{-1} \left(Y_{TG} + Y_{TL} (Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1} Y_{LG} \right) \right] \quad (\text{A.20})
\end{aligned}$$

the generator voltages and currents can be related by

$$I_G = Y_{eq}V_G$$

where Y_{eq} is a matrix that models the equivalent admittances connecting the loads to the generators, as well as the equivalent admittances of lines connecting the generators to each other.

A.3 Ward Feedback Method

In order to express generator currents as a function of load voltages and currents for feedback control, a modified 3-section Ward reduction can be used. Once again, the admittance matrix is divided into three areas for the generator, transmission, and load buses.

$$\begin{pmatrix} I_G \\ 0 \\ I_L \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} Y_{GG} & Y_{GT} & Y_{GL} \\ Y_{TG} & Y_{TT} & Y_{TL} \\ Y_{LG} & Y_{LT} & Y_{LL} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} V_G \\ V_T \\ V_L \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

The transmission bus voltages can be computed as

$$V_T = (-Y_{TT})^{-1}[Y_{TG}V_G + Y_{TL}V_L]. \quad (\text{A.22})$$

The load current can then be found by substituting equation (A.22) into the third row of equation (A.21)

$$I_L = [Y_{GL} + Y_{LT}(-Y_{TT})^{-1}Y_{TG}]V_G + [Y_{LL} + Y_{LT}(-Y_{TT})^{-1}Y_{TL}]V_L. \quad (\text{A.23})$$

from which the generator voltage V_G can be found and put in the form

$$V_G = [Y_{GL} + Y_{LT}(-Y_{LL})^{-1}Y_{TG}]^+ [I_L - (Y_{LL} + Y_{LT}(-Y_{TT})^{-1}Y_{TL})V_L] \quad (\text{A.24})$$

where the (+) superscript denotes the Moore-Penrose pseudo-inverse. A pseudo-inverse must be used in this case, as Y_{GL} is not necessarily square. Finally, the generator current can be calculated by substituting equation (A.22) and equation (A.24) into the first row of equation (A.21)

$$\begin{aligned} I_G = & \left(Y_{GG} + Y_{GT}(-Y_{TT})^{-1}Y_{TG} \right) [Y_{GL} + Y_{LT}(Y_L - Y_{LL})^{-1}Y_{TG}]^+ [I_L - \\ & - (Y_{LL} + Y_{LT}(-Y_{TT})^{-1}Y_{TL})V_L] + \\ & + \left(Y_{GL} + Y_{GT}(-Y_{TT})^{-1}Y_{TL} \right) V_L. \quad (\text{A.25}) \end{aligned}$$

This gives the generator currents in terms of load voltages and currents. This allows the flat outputs of the generators to be determined by the voltage and current at the loads. Notice that derivatives can be taken directly on both sides, as the admittances are all constants.

APPENDIX B

POLYNOMIAL TRAJECTORY PLANNING

Polynomial interpolation is a simple method to create functions that satisfy trivial control needs, such as moving between steady state constants, while at the same time satisfying needs of sufficient smoothness.

B.1 Polynomial Fitting Between Two Steady States

Interpolation between desired constant values via polynomial interpolation as is typically used in path planning for robotics, explained in Siciliano et al [18]. The major difference in this application, however, is that higher order polynomials must be used to ensure sufficient smoothness as higher order derivatives will be taken than is typical in kinematics. Our desired trajectories, $I_{D_{des}}$ and $I_{Q_{des}}$, will have the form

$$I_{D_{des}} + jI_{Q_{des}} = \begin{cases} I_D + jI_Q & t < t_1 \\ I_D + jI_Q + \left(\sum_{k=0}^7 \alpha_k t^k \right) (I_{D_\Delta} + jI_{Q_\Delta}) & t_1 \leq t < t_2 \\ I_D + jI_Q + (I_{D_\Delta} + jI_{Q_\Delta}) & t \geq t_2 \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Where α_k are the coefficients of a polynomial that is 0 at t_1 and 1 at t_2 . All derivatives of the polynomial are zero at t_1 and t_2 . The currents I_{D_Δ} and I_{Q_Δ} are the difference between the desired final current and the initial current. The polynomial coefficients, α , are calculated by solving the matrix equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & t_1 & t_1^2 & \dots & t_1^7 \\ 0 & 1 & 2t_1 & \dots & 7t_1^6 \\ \vdots & & \ddots & & \vdots \\ 0 & & \dots & & 210t_1^4 \\ 1 & t_2 & t_2^2 & \dots & t_2^7 \\ 0 & 1 & 2t_2 & \dots & 7t_2^6 \\ \vdots & & \ddots & & \vdots \\ 0 & & \dots & & 210t_2^4 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \alpha_0 \\ \alpha_1 \\ \vdots \\ \alpha_7 \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

for the vector of α 's, which are the polynomial coefficients . The vector of 1's and 0's are constraints for the polynomial to satisfy, here having a initial value of 0 and a final value of 1, as well as having zero derivatives at the boundaries t_1 and t_2 . The matrix correspond to the structure of the polynomial and it's derivatives.

B.2 Polynomial Perturbation Function

The polynomial perturbation function is similar to the steady-state to steady-state polynomial in the previous section, except that the function reaches a maximum, then returns to the original steady state. Such a desired current trajectory would have the form

$$I_{D_{des}} + jI_{Q_{des}} = \begin{cases} I_D + jI_Q & t < t_1 \\ I_D + jI_Q + \Delta \left(\sum_{k=0}^7 \alpha_k t^k \right) & t_1 \leq t < t_2 \\ I_D + jI_Q + \Delta \left(\sum_{k=0}^7 \beta_k t^k \right) & t_2 \leq t < t_3 \\ I_D + jI_Q & t \geq t_3 \end{cases} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where α_k are the coefficients of a polynomial that is 0 at t_1 and 1 at t_2 , with derivatives equal to zero at these points, as in equation (B.1). The coefficients β_k define a polynomial that is 1 at t_2 and 0 at t_3 , with derivatives equal to zero at those points. The scalar value Δ defines the maximum of the perturbation, $I_{D_{max}} + jI_{Q_{max}}$. The coefficients α_k and β_k are both found using the same linear algebra techniques as used in equation (B.2).

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Glover, M. Sarma, and T. Overbye, *Power Systems Analysis and Design*. Cengage Learning, 2007.
- [2] P. Kundur, N. Balu, and M. Lauby, *Power System Stability and Control*. EPRI power system engineering series, McGraw-Hill, 1994.
- [3] P. Sauer and A. Pai, *Power System Dynamics and Stability*. Stipes Publishing L.L.C., 2006.
- [4] P. Kundur, J. Paserba, V. Ajjarapu, G. Andersson, A. Bose, C. Canizares, N. Hatziargyriou, D. Hill, A. Stankovic, C. Taylor, T. Van Cutsem, and V. Vittal, "Definition and classification of power system stability IEEE/CIGRE joint task force on stability terms and definitions," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 19, pp. 1387–1401, Aug 2004.
- [5] E. Sontag, *Mathematical Control Theory: Deterministic Finite Dimensional Systems*. Texts in Applied Mathematics, U.S. Government Printing Office, 1998.
- [6] M. Vidyasagar, *Nonlinear Systems Analysis: Second Edition*. Classics in Applied Mathematics, Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics, 2002.
- [7] F. Mak, *Analysis and control of voltage dynamics in electric power systems*. PhD thesis, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, 1990.
- [8] J. Chapman, M. Ilic, C. A. King, L. Eng, and H. Kaufman, "Stabilizing a multimachine power system via decentralized feedback linearizing excitation control," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 8, pp. 830–839, Aug 1993.
- [9] P. Martin, R. M. Murray, and P. Rouchon, "Flat systems, equivalence and trajectory generation," tech. rep., California Institute of Technology, 2003.
- [10] J. Lévine, *Analysis and Control of Nonlinear Systems: a Flatness-based Approach*. Mathematical engineering, Berlin, London: Springer, 2009.
- [11] P. Martin and P. Rouchon, "Two remarks on induction motors," *CESA'96 IMACS Multiconference*, pp. 76–79, 1996.
- [12] K. Glass, R. Colbaugh, and K. Wedeward, "Control of differentially flat mechanical systems in the presence of uncertainty," *Proceedings of the American Control Conference*, pp. 3836–3838, 1997.

- [13] H. Sira-Ramirez and M. Ilic-Spong, "Exact linearization in switched-mode DC-to-DC power converters," *International Journal of Control*, vol. 50, pp. 511–524, 1989.
- [14] Octave community, "GNU Octave 3.6.4," 2014.
- [15] J. B. Ward, "Equivalent circuits for power-flow studies," *Transactions of The American Institute of Electrical Engineers*, vol. 68, pp. 373–382, July 1949.
- [16] T. Baldwin, L. Mili, and A. Phadke, "Dynamic ward equivalents for transient stability analysis," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 9, pp. 59–67, Feb 1994.
- [17] I. Hiskens and J. Alseddiqui, "Sensitivity, approximation, and uncertainty in power system dynamic simulation," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 21, pp. 1808–1820, Nov 2006.
- [18] B. Siciliano, L. Sciavicco, G. Oriolo, and L. Villani, *Robotics: Modelling, Planning and Control*. Advanced Textbooks in Control and Signal Processing, Springer, 2010.